

ISic1484

I.Sicily inscription 1484

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

limestone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

2015.07.02

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Gela

Place of origin (modern)

Gela

Provenance

Capo Soprano, foundations of the villa of Conte Panebianco

Coordinates**Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico
Regionale Paolo Orsi, inventory 19817

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 644992

Bibliography

Dubois, L. 1989. Inscriptions grecques dialectales de Sicile : contribution à l'étude du vocabulaire grec colonial. Rome. At 130 (http://www.persee.fr/doc/efr_0000-0000_1989_cat_119_1)

undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined 1876-.

Notizie degli scavi di antichità. *Notizie degli scavi di antichità*. At 281-282 fig.4

Bechtel, F., Collitz, H., Meister, R. C., Bezenberger, A. 1884-1915. Sammlung der

griechischen Dialekt-Inschriften. Göttingen. At 5216

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